

PROSPECTS FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF LOGISTICS SYSTEMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada globallashuv sharoitida xalqaro va milliy logistika tizimlarining ahamiyati, ularning iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishdagi roli va raqamlashtirish jarayonlarining ta'siri tahlil qilinadi,. Shuningdek, logistika markazlarining infratuzilmaviy tuzilishi va qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini tashishdagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlari yoritib berilgan,.

Kalit so'zlar

xalqaro logistika, raqamli iqtisodiyot, ta'minot zanjiri, logistika markazlari, transport infratuzilmasi, qishloq xo'jaligi logistikasi.

Аннотация

В данной статье анализируется значение международных и национальных логистических систем в условиях глобализации, их роль в повышении экономической эффективности, а также влияние процессов цифровизации. Кроме того, освещаются инфраструктурная структура логистических центров и их специфические особенности в сфере транспортировки сельскохозяйственной продукции.

Ключевые слова:

международная логистика, цифровая экономика, цепь поставок, логистические центры, транспортная инфраструктура, агрологистика.

Annotation

This article analyzes the importance of international and national logistics systems in the context of globalization, their role in increasing economic efficiency, as well as the impact of digitalization processes. In addition, the infrastructural structure of logistics centers and their specific features in the transportation of agricultural products are highlighted.

Keywords

international logistics, digital economy, supply chain, logistics centers, transport infrastructure, agricultural logistics.

Introduction

Today, the deepening of globalization processes and the increase in international trade volumes are radically increasing the role of the logistics system. International logistics is the process of planning and controlling the flow of goods, services and information on an inter-country scale. Since Uzbekistan is geo-economically located in the center of Central Asia, at the intersection of transport corridors, the development of this sector is a decisive factor in increasing the competitiveness of the republic's foreign trade. Theoretical foundations of the logistics system Logistics is the process of effectively coordinating the movement of material resources and finished products. The international logistics system consists of several main components, including transport, warehousing, customs services and information flow management. Incoterms (international trade terms) rules play an important role in organizing these processes, allocating costs and risks in delivery. Supply chain management (SCM) covers all stages of the product from the raw material state to the consumer.

The importance of logistics centers and infrastructure The largest infrastructure facility in the transport process is logistics centers (LM). LM is a hub that provides transportation, storage and cargo distribution services on a commercial basis in a given area. The establishment of such centers outside the city limits helps to reduce traffic congestion and improve the environmental situation. One of the important components of the logistics infrastructure is the "Dry Port", which, in conjunction with sea ports, allows customs clearance and sorting of cargo in inland areas.

Digitalization and Innovation in Logistics Processes In the digital economy, data is becoming a key factor of production. Artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies are increasing supply chain efficiency. According to research, companies that use AI have reduced logistics costs by 15% and optimized inventory by 35%. Digital platforms expand the opportunities for small businesses to enter global markets.

Features of logistics in agricultural production

Since agricultural products are perishable, special conditions (refrigeration, temperature control) are required for their transportation and storage. Effective organization of commercial logistics not only helps to maintain product quality, but also helps to develop export potential by reducing excess transportation costs.

Conclusion Improving the logistics system is a prerequisite for sustainable growth of the national economy. This requires the modernization of transport infrastructure, the widespread introduction of digital technologies, and the training of highly qualified personnel. An integrated approach will create the opportunity to minimize logistics costs and increase the attractiveness of products in the global market

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